

ZURO

1969

THE MAGAZINE OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY
UMTALI BOYS' HIGH SCHOOL

EDITORIAL.

The membership of our History Society is drawn from Form III and above. These students have therefore been studying senior School history for anything between three and perhaps eight years, and yet I wonder how many of us, not only the society members, have ever considered why we are made to learn History (I use 'made' here purposely for few of us, I think originally pursued the subject of our own free will). Ostensibly we learn history to pass an exam to get a Certificate to procure a job in the wide world, geared to the present and the future but not to the past and where 1066 and 1492 are soon forgotten.

However scratch the surface of history and most people who bother find interest and an importance to modern day living well beyond their expectations. The study of history brings to light patterns of human behavior, important for all time. Students learn to observe more acutely their subject matter, to discriminate between various schools of thought and subsequently to draw their own conclusions. In doing this research is naturally of supreme importance, not only in order to obtain a wide knowledge of the facts, viewed from various angles, but also to hold and increase the students interest. It is true for many of us that a piece of work well done is a piece of work for which we have read widely, having background knowledge as well as the pertinent facts at our finger-tips before we write. Our research for class essays and projects involves the use of reference books only, which often, though unintentionally, tend to dampen the spirit in which the research is undertaken.

Nevertheless, active research is far removed from these dry-as-dust biographies and encyclopaedias, and this year the History Society has brought history out of its usual context in schools - that of a purely academic subject, and involved many of the members in active research. The boys and girls have been gleaning information wherever possible for "A History of Government Education in Untali." They could not use reference books as none have been written on the subject - theirs was the first. Their research involved visiting archives, talking to elderly people who had been connected with the school and in certain cases with children and grandchildren of people important in the field of education in Untali. There is much to be said of information obtained in this way as opposed to the normal research we undertake. Firstly information obtained from contemporary sources or at most, second hand, is that much more interesting and alive; more reliable as it is closer to the reality of the time than if it were taken from Modern History books. Much of interest can be unearthed by talking to people and the researcher must experience a definite sense of achievement from the production of a history such as the one brought out in June of this year.

The importance of research cannot be under-estimated - it is important in the understanding of history as being more than a purely academic subject taught in the class room, more than a dead study of situations bearing no relevance to the present. Instead it makes history a living study of the past which is inextricably tied up with the present and the future.

CAROL STEWART. UVI.

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CHAIRMAN'S REPORT.

	<u>1968/1969</u>	<u>1969/1970</u>
Chairman	P. Lark	G. Molloy
Secretary	J. Finch	C. De Villiers
Treasurer	McGaugiano	T. Scott
Committee Member	C. Stewart	D. Gilmour

1969, the Society's second year has been most successful as far as the activities of the Society are concerned. While the membership was still a little thin, it was an improvement over last year and it is to be hoped will be further improved in the future.

The completion of the School history magazine and its subsequent publication in the second term of this year must be regarded as the society's best achievement. While all those concerned are too numerous to name Mr. Finch deserves special mention for the work he did. All those concerned were treated to a cheese and punch party by Mr. Davidge on the completion of the work.

As far as outings were concerned, only one was held on the 16th February, the society made a trip to Rusape. Those who went saw both Zimbabwe and Inyanga type ruins as well as some bushmen paintings, and a good time was had by all. A proposed excursion to Meikle's farm in conjunction with the town Museum Society fell through due to a lack of support. The proposed Sofala trip which was to have taken place over Rhodes & Founders had to be called off as it would have proved too costly.

The society has had a most successful year as regards meetings. On February 14th, Mr. Davidge gave an interest talk on the source of the Nile, well illustrated with maps. On March 7th, Mr. Taylor from U.C.R. gave an amusing account of the early Native department. On March 21st Mr. Lewis gave a talk on his P.C.W. experiences during the Second World War. As regards contents and attendance this was the most successful meeting held. On June 13th Mr. Davidge organised a cultural evening, spoilt only through a lack of attendance. On June 20th Mr. Palframan gave a well informed talk on Versailles and it is to be hoped that more schoolboys can be persuaded to give talks. On July 30th Mr. Dickinson from U.C.R. gave a talk on Sofala, illustrated with slides. We are thankful to the above mentioned for helping to make the society's activities a success.

Unfortunately our founder, Mr. Davidge is leaving us at the end of the year and to him and his successor we wish every success for the future.

So with the society now a firmly established part of the School we look forward to an even more successful third year.

P. LARK. L.VI.

MINUTES OF MEETINGS HELD BY THE
HISTORY SOCIETY.

14th February, 1969.

Speaker : Mr. B. Davidge.
Topic : "The Source of the Nile".

Mr. Davidge began by introducing us to the main characters. Two of the most important were Burton and Speke, who in June, 1857 had set off for the mainland from Zanzibar. Burton, who was described as being "more Arab than the Arabs" was already a well known explorer, swordsman of note and skilled linguist. Speke was a less accomplished person but had a flair for the unexplored Africa. Unfortunately both became ill by the time they reached Ujiji. They returned to Kazi and from here made further investigations. Speke after a trip to London returned in 1860 with Grant. Baker then followed them out in 1863 but perhaps the most important character was Dr. Livingstone. Livingstone made an incredible series of wanderings, his last journey taking him from 1866 until 1873. He was succeeded by Stanley (of the famous "Dr. Livingstone I presume"). Stanley in his boat, Lady Alice, sailed around Lake Victoria, saw the Ripon Falls and met Mutesa and envoys from Gordon Pasha. Stanley found that Speke's view about the source were correct and after sailing around Lake Tanganyika reached the mouth of the Congo on 1877. He was succeeded by Chailli-Long, an American who travelled as far as Kasuma.

Mr. Davidge illustrated his very informative talk with maps and diagrams.

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17th March, 1969.

Speaker : Mr. Taylor.
Topic : "Early Native Department".

Mr. Taylor who is writing a thesis on the early African Administration in Rhodesia told us that he had begun his work in the Salisbury Archives. The initial work was going through reports and letters but some of the earliest papers were not available and he had to turn to other sources. Also much of the information that existed was by and large superficial. However he was fortunate in that a friend of his was going around the country visiting pioneers and interviewing them. This proved a great help as did interviews of the Chiefs and Africans on the Tribal lands. He found that old traditions were still very strong with the African and therefore the chronology of events was more important to them than to Europeans. Newspapers he said were also important.

Mr. Taylor started the actual history with basic things such as who was in the Native Department? He outlined the early administration

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which by the end of 1894 had been divided up into different parts under the Native Commissioner. At this time James Brabant was appointed the first Chief Native Commissioner.

The early Commissioners were never qualified men but were usually tough people who never went down with illnesses such as blackwater. These men were looked on by the African as being a "Chief" but the Commissioner had to be careful for not gaining too much power. This was because the real chief of the tribe may take a dislike to the administration. These Commissioners also married African women as a sort of alliance. The marriage, however, was not christian but traditional.

Some of the Commissioners were very conscientious men and took great trouble in finding out the history of the tribe as well as the customs. These notes, Mr. Taylor said, proved of great assistance.

Mr. Taylor summed up by saying that the subject's interest is only real when you delve into it.

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27th March, 1969.

Speaker : Mr. Harris.

Topic : "Experiences in Prisoner of War Camps during the Second World War".

The attendance at this meeting was the most successful we have ever had and Mr. Harris gave an extremely interesting and informative speech. He illustrated his talk with diagrams and certain souvenirs of the Prisoners of War. Mr. Harris was 19 when he joined the Air Force and because war broke out so suddenly he found himself a regular. He joined the 44 Squadron which later became the Rhodesian Squadron. In August, 1940 after a raid over Berlin his Canadian pilot attempted to get straight home - Mr. Harris wanted to stop over at Sweden. The starboard engine failed over Holland but the pilot made a miracle landing.

After setting fire to the plane they attempted a daring escape through a village. Unfortunately for them a cleaner woman whose son was in the Luftwaffe tipped off the Germans and Mr. Harris became P.O.W. Number 184. He was put in a cell which he described as being too small to lie down and like a "cold storage" at night. He was questioned but was to prove most unco-operative. However he did find out a number of things he did not know himself. He also met the other British prisoners and said "It was good but at the same time tragic to meet the chaps."

Mr. Harris was then moved to the north coast where he experienced terrible conditions. The food was awful and Mr. Harris normally 180 lbs. came down to 74! Currency was based on cigarettes and to keep up their spirits the prisoners tried almost anything. Mr. Harris described their rugby games as being "quite pathetic but yet it was an effort."

Mr. Harris taught French and Maths to the prisoners. Toilet paper made up for exercise books and people passed Cambridge examinations on this work. Unfortunately on occasions the ship carrying the papers sank and the prisoners had no reward for three years' work.

Five attempts were made to escape. On one occasion he escaped by the Russian border while hidden in some rubbish and using a tube to breathe through. He was out for three weeks before being caught and brought back. Mr. Harris also saw the Great Escape and Wooden Horse Escape and played a part in them.

Other interesting happenings included the blowing up of a German power station, seeing Hitler when marching through Berlin and meeting Douglas Bader in the Prisoner of War Camp.

15th June, 1969.

Topic : Cultural Evening arranged by Mr. Davidge.

Mr. Davidge first explained that the evening would be a general pot-pourri of culture and society during the 18th, 19th and 20th centuries with the theme being that "an individual reflects the social, political and economic developments of a country." Mr. Davidge also gave a brief account of the period to be covered and at the conclusion of this showed art slides of 18th century accompanied by music.

Then Mr. Nick Reynolds read a verse from William Wordsworth followed by Miss Carol Stewart reading John Keats' "Ode to a Nightingale." This was followed by a short excerpt from Wagner's "Flying Dutchman" after which Mr. David Gilmour read extracts from "Les Châtiments" by Victor Hugo. This satirical account clearly showed the trend away from Romanticism towards Realism.

After two more slides were shown, this time of works of art by the Impressionists. The proceedings were brought to an end by Mr. Chris. Moore who read a piece on the "Culture of Crisis." He said that the creative artist, having had his sensitivity shocked by the 1914 - 18 war broke away from the traditional established beliefs resulting in the grim realism and brutality found in Hemmingway and T.S. Eliot's new form of poetry.

On the whole this proved a very entertaining evening despite the small attendance.

20th June, 1969.

Speaker - Mr. Ivan Palfreman.
Topic - "Treaty of Versailles."

Mr. Palfreman explained in excellent detail the Treaty, the characters and some of the repercussions. Signed on June 28, 1919 it contained 15 parts. Part I dealt with the Covenant of the League of Nations; II and III with territorial dispositions, Germany losing Alsace and Lorraine to France, several frontier districts to Belgium, Denmark, Poland and Lithuania, while the banks of the Rhine were demilitarised; the Saar basin was placed under an international commission, with German's colonial possessions which were then mandated to the Chief Allied Powers; Part V restricted her armaments while VIII and IX dealt with Reparations and finance; X with economic restitution, commercial treaties, etc.; XII with transport, shipping, etc. XIII provided for the setting up of an international labour organisation; Part XIV provided for military occupation of the Rhine Zone by the Allies. The other parts dealt with prisoners, war graves, etc.

He also discussed the characters of Woodrow Wilson (United States), Lloyd George (Great Britain) and Clemenceau (France) and after his talk discussion was thrown open to the floor. This proved to be very interesting and the Chairman was forced to interrupt with respect to the time. One member pointed out that Woodrow Wilson had at this time lost his support in the American Congress and should not have been allowed to make any decisions. Mr. Barnes brought up an interesting point when he said that German in fact gained from the settlement because she borrowed more than she paid. Discussion of these points and a number of others made it a very interesting evening.

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30th July, 1969.

Speaker - Mr. Dickinson.
Topic - "Sofala".

Mr. Dickinson firstly gave us an outline of Sofala's history. In the 10th century the Arabs came to Sofala in small boats (not dhows because of the beaching difficulty due to the sand bar.) They brought the Africans beads and cloth in return for ivory. Towards the end of the 15th century, the Portuguese entered the picture. They brought stone with them to build a fort which also served as a ballast as ships had no keel. Pedro d'Anhaya was the leader of this group. The Portuguese made a trading agreement with the 70 year old ruler Sheik Ysuf, a Moor. They traded cheap, brightly coloured gifts for gold. However conflict arose between the Sheik and the Portuguese, for instead of building a trading store the latter built a fort. The Portuguese overwhelmed the locals and the Sheik Ysuf was beheaded - a new Sheik was instituted whom the Portuguese could control. The Arabs, however, merely moved the gold trade north along the Zambezi.

Mr. Dickinson also spoke of the local people and their ways. It is interesting to note that they do not live in vast villages and have two huts - one to sleep in and one to cook in. As there were some 125 men and only three women amongst the settlers they married the natives.

Today Sofala is a place of historic interest and some of the old buildings are still standing including the Mahomedan tombs though the fort has been dismantled and only the foundations can be seen at low tide.

A VISIT TO THE RUSAPE AREA.

On 16th February a party of three girls and seven boys accompanied by Mr. Davidge and Miss Shaw set out for Rusape to see some rock paintings and some ruins of archaeological interest.

We went first to Diana's Vow where we saw some bushman paintings on a large overhanging rock - they were in good condition and stood out well when splashed with water. A few hundred yards away we found ruins of the Inyanga type seen at Ziwa last year, among them two low lintled entrances.

After this we set out by truck again and after a few miles came to further ruins at Harleigh Farm. There were two sets of ruins here, about half-a-mile apart. The first lot was obviously a grave yard - a rocky outcrop had been walled-in, in certain places and the whole area surrounded by a stone wall three to four feet high. What was peculiar was the fact that clay had been used as mortar in the building of the walls - neither Ziwa nor Zimbabwe type ruins make any use of mortar.

After lunch we walked a few hundred yards to some further ruins. These were definitely of the Zimbabwe type, again peculiarly so as there is no further evidence of any architecture of this variety around Rusape - Inyanga. A fairly large area had been walled in by high walls built in the sophisticated or 'Q' style walling with all the stones cut to similar sizes, roughly brick shaped but five to six times bigger. We also saw some bushman paintings here consisting mainly of animal studies. There was a suspicion of a hunt scene.

We then set out to see the 'Pink Elephant' paintings just off the main Inyanga road but as it was getting late and looked like rain we had to forego this and we hope to try again at a later date.

We arrived back in Untali at 6.00 p.m. having had an interesting and enjoyable time.

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THUGS : A MYTHOLOGICAL AND HISTORICAL STUDY.

The modern definition of the word thug is a youngster or a long haired trouble-causing lout but few people realise that behind the true meaning of the word thug linger well over one million murders.

The thugs originally were members of thuggees (as their association was called) a well organized religious confederacy of professional assassins. Their religion is, perhaps, the only one in history which was based solely on murder and its rewards. Very simply they were gangs who roamed the northern and central provinces of India; winning themselves into the confidence of wayfarers, waiting until a favourable opportunity occurred when in accordance with ancient and religious rites they murdered them.

This bizarre religion was founded on Late Epic Hindu Mythology: the Creator of Life gave spirit to men and women who, in turn, began to populate the earth. After this beginning came Raktabij Danaval (Demon of Blood and Seed) whose purpose was to maintain a balance between birth and death. However, contrary to the Creator's wishes, he instead killed men as soon as they were created. Soon the earth was empty - no life could exist. A Goddess Kali (Dark Mother - cult title of Durga, wife of Siva) whose attributes were enigmatical, though she is normally regarded as the Goddess of Death and Destruction - was sent to combat the defiant Demon. Using her destroying sword she cut deep into the Demon's flesh. His blood and seed poured from his mortal wound. From each drop that fell to the ground a new demon arose. These began to kill men as they were created - Kali hacked at the new-born demons only to see more spring up from their spilt blood. Kali now exhausted, rested to wipe the sweat of fruitless effort from her brow with her handkerchief (rumal). While doing this two drops of perspiration fell from her arms to the ground.

The Creator observing her distress fashioned two men from these drops of sweat and they were called Servants of Kali. Kali gave them her rumal and commanded them to strangle all the Demons - thus spilling of their blood was avoided. They obeyed, completed the task and made to return the rumal to the Goddess. But she bade them keep it for use as an implement of a profitable trade. Now she declared mankind owed them men, even until the last reckoning. She bestowed on them the right to live off the rewards of murder; on condition they obeyed her requests and signs they would prosper. One third of the profits had to be given to her. It is from these two men in the myth, that the future associations of thugs have evolved but to appreciate the beliefs of the thugs it is necessary to study their methods and organisation, in some depth. Each Thuggee operated as a skilled individual unit. In charge of the unit was the Jemadar (leader) and under him served various officers and men, they were, in descending rank:- the priest, gang's teacher, qualified stranglers (who were graded according to experience) spies and lastly the grave diggers.

The religious rites performed, before and after their atrocious crimes were committed, were of a complex nature and must be followed from the beginning of their "season". After the Dassehra (a festival to celebrate the end of the monsoon rains) travellers (e.g. merchants) would take to the now dry roads, followed closely by the thugs. From a camp near a village spies probed the markets for suitable "beetod" (merchandise - victims). On selecting a small party about to travel, the smooth tongued

spy would join them, elaborate on the dangers of travelling in minority groups without an escort, eventually persuading them to join his group for mutual protection. The party of thugs and "beetoo" spent a few days travelling in jovial companionship, so lulling the "beetoo" into a sense of false security. The nights were spent in groves (clearings just off the roadside) and it was one of these that the Jamadar would select as the Chil (place selected for killing). Before night fell on the day chosen for the slaughter, the Jamadar, priest and stranglers would meet in a pre-arranged spot after unobtrusively slipping away from the wayfarers in the grove. A brief religious ceremony was then conducted by the organisation's priest. The priest would lay a consecrated pick-axe on a sacred cloth, the axe head pointing in the direction they were journeying. The priest then prayed to Kali "O Kali, thy servants are waiting, grant them thy approval". The expectant group then waited for the Goddess to grant them the recognised omen, indicating the time was ripe for the death of the "beetoo". The sign they desired was an animal call from the left followed immediately by another from the right. No sign meant no murders. If the "good omen" was received, the priest then handed a new rupee, blessed in the name of Kali to each strangler, who then knotted it in a corner of his rumal (this was a piece of cloth three feet square). The rumals were then consecrated and returned to the loin-cloth with just a small corner showing, so facilitating its reach. They then discreetly wound their way back to their places of rest in the grove.

The wheels of motion turned smoothly and that evening the thugs appeared to be in a more convivial mood than they had been on any of the other previous nights. Sitting around the fires or fire, stories flowed easily and the music would be sweet. (Most thuggee had a man of musical ability in their ranks). No one would notice the natural way in which the stranglers took up key positions behind their allotted victims. Only the thugs regarded the man - a grave digger usually - who slunk up to the leader and whispered in his ear "The graves are dug Jamadar - sahib."

On a pre-arranged code word from the Jamadar, such as "the stars are bright", the stranglers working in pairs or singly went into action. The rumal (or in some cases a slip-noose) was swung, the corner with the weighted rupee whirled round the "beetoo's" throat, into the strangler's left hand where the rupee formed a grip. The rumal was then positioned round the victim's neck, the stranger's wrists being against the side of the neck, just under the ear. In one swift movement the wrists were pressed together, the knuckles turned inwards, the strangler's knees placed in the small of the back, then with a savage effort the wrists were jerked back and up to one side. The prey either died of a broken neck or by strangulation. It was a quick, efficient but cruel death. Accordingly no blood was shed at the scene of the crime.

The Thuggee only disposed of small groups that could easily be overcome by sheer weight of numbers (average band of thugs had about 15 members). Even if, for example, a traveller or beetoo had departed from the party for any reason - he was followed by a number of thugs and duly killed. This prevented him passing on the news further up the trail that a party of travellers were coming that way.

After the murder, the corpses were stripped of all worth-while

belongings, e.g. jewellery, money but never clothing, and then the inert bodies were dragged to the grave in the jungle. By this large pit terrible mutilations took place. First the bodies in turn were positioned across a large log and the joints smashed with a heavy club - a broken body required less room than a whole one. Next the crushed cadavers had their bellies split open with sharp bamboo stakes to release the gases of decomposition; so preventing the stomachs swelling and disrupting the earth over the grave. The disjointed bodies were then thrown into the grave along with their useless remaining possession, the stakes, log and club being placed on top of them. Careful covering and concealment of the mass grave was then carried out. Seeds of fleawort (peppery seed) were scattered over the area to stop wild animals from disturbing the graves. The spoils were then divided among the thugs each collecting a set percentage as based on his rank.

A thanksgiving service - a ceremony of communion with Kali was held in the morning. To "Dark Mother" they expressed their gratitude for allowing the booty to fall into their hands. Prayers of continued allegiance were said and the thugs promised to maintain her glory asking in return for their services, Kali's blessings and guidance. Then came the sacrifice of sugar. A consecrated rupee coated in sugar was buried over the grave; the priest then beckoned the stranglers to stand on the sacred cloth, on which lay the consecrated pickaxe - this act enabled Kali to enter them. All present were required to eat a piece of consecrated (given to Jemadar and stranglers) or unconsecrated (given to rest of thugs) sugar, while the priest recited these words, "Take eat, this is the sweetness of Kali. You are hers and she is yours". This superstitious act bound the thuggee body together for no thug would dare to incur Kali's wrath by informing on the system "you are hers".

The practice of thuggee was of considerable antiquity. It is mentioned in a 14th century history and probably dates back much further. During the reign of Shah Jahan (17th century Mughal emperor who built the Taj Mahal) de Threvenot, a French traveller reported the road between Pelhi and Ayra infested by thugs "the cunningest robbers in the world. . they use a certain slip with a running noose which they can cast with so much slight about a man's neck when they are within reach of him, that they never fail, so that they strangle him in a trice."

The country, built on superstition, was itself in a state of anarchy and political chaos. Landowners regarded robbery and murder as a sport, various neighbouring villages were in a state of constant feuding, there were no true Indian courts to which a peasant could take a complaint, bribery and corruption was virtually the hall mark of every state.

It was only after 1823 that a majority of India really came under the influence of Great Britain. Part of the land, notably Madras and Bengal were governed through the great East India Company. Other territories were still native states but recognised British authority in certain respects the chief of these was Hyderabad, Mysore and the group of states comprised in the territory called the Rajputana, such as Jaipure. However it was not until 1856 that the British eventually absorbed areas of this nature. Thus the local authority particularly in the northern and central provinces, was extended over the populace by the rajahs, squires or landowners. A large number of these rulers were in league with the thugs, operating their own gangs or demanding a share of the thuggee's profit in return for permission to operate within their territory. If they did not receive this "protection

money" the thuggee concerned was punished but not destroyed as their system benefitted them financially. Once the British investigated the thugs operations the rajahs were only too willing to turn on their past allies.

On the roads none knew where a traveller came from or where he was going to. Thus it was difficult to trace a deceased person.

Before 1825 sporadic efforts had been made towards the extinction of the gangs. British tax collectors (who handled the civil administration in their districts) wrote reports on their activities, (these were in the main pigeon-holed) and the band chased away only to flourish in a new locality. The higher authorities were not at first aware of the gravity of the situation - they took on an aloof attitude of disbelief.

The disappearance of young sepoy on leave made the British take, what they had merely considered stories before, seriously. However; it was left to Captain William Sleeman (1788 - 1856) of the Indian Political Service to prove the existence of the powerful thug confederacy operating over the whole of northern India, where the Rajah of Jaintia in Assam, had even sacrificed British subjects to Kali.

In 1829, in the course of his reforms the Governor-General of India, Lord William Bentinck (1828 - 1835) authorised a special department to investigate and destroy the practice of Thuggee and Sleeman was placed in charge of the whole operation in 1835. In 1839 he was appointed Commissioner for the Suppression of Thuggee and Dacoity.

The bands were hard to track down; they sold the stolen goods cunningly so that it was difficult to trace the goods back to them; they were "too small, secret, and tenuous to be caught by cavalry; too large and mobile for the watchmen." But the British were determined to suppress thuggee once they had grasped its proportions and they attacked the organisation with single-minded energy. In 1836 an Act was passed whereby it was made a criminal offence to be associated with a band of thugs - the penalty for this crime was transportation.

When a thuggee was caught, a member of the gang usually turned informer, in order to save his own skin. He would confess, implicating others, providing corroborative evidence by pointing out the graves; others of the gangs would then normally hurry forward to gain a pardon. The informers of which there were 483 by 1837 were detained in special prisons, the principal one being at Gubbulpore, (for their own protection).

Sleeman, with the co-operation of a number of native states succeeded so well in grappling with the evil that between 1831 and 1837 no fewer than 3,266 thugs were captured of whom 412 were hung. The remainder either turned informer, were transported or imprisoned for life. Condemned thugs appeared to suffer no remorse. One confessed to 719 killings but his only regret was that he had been caught before he could reach his target of 1,000 murders. It had been estimated that at the commencement of anti-thuggee operations, there

were 10,000 thugs at large killing between 20,000 and 30,000 travellers a year, by 1837 it was estimated that only 2,000 remained in the field.

It had been a long weary business, there was very little excitement and danger - the occasional thuggee resisted rather than surrendered. The accused came before the Judges of the East India Co. who required clear corroborated, uncontradicted testimony - any discrepancy in court was taken as a sign of innocence, no matter how guilty the person really was. Nevertheless it was through this slow plodding law system that the Indians began to observe their British rulers in a new light - now they were offered at last a form of protection and stable government.

It is ironical that after surviving for hundreds of years whereby the profession was passed down from father to son, it was uncovered and uprooted shortly before the coming of the railway and telegraph to India which would have destroyed it.

According to the Thuggee and Dacoity report for 1879 registered Punjabi and Hindustani thugs then still numbered 384. But all of these had already been registered as such before 1852; the whole fraternity thereafter became extinct though the office of Superintendent of the Thuggee and Dacoity was maintained until 1904.

References: "Raj" by Michael Edwards.
"The Deceivers" by John Masters.
"A History of India" by Powell-Price.
"The Founders" by Woodruff.
"The Groundwork of British History" by Warner, Marten & Muir.
"Consolidated Encyclopaedia"
"Encyclopaedia Britannica".

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CORRESPONDENCE.

Dear Madam,

"History is bunk" seems to be the general concensus of opinion to-day. However, disregarding this there are some human beings who can make history become vibrantly alive - these few are normally regarded as being highly imaginative people. But this is not so, for history can and does serve a purpose, it does not only chronicle the antiquity of bygone ages. If you have any aspirations towards truly understanding man or even if you desire to study the subconscious mind, then history should be one of your methods of choice.

Take for example, military history, which is inseparable from general civilian history through whose study you can feel for the inner man (true personality colours only show under fire) and even relive the rigours of trenchwarfare.

Sir Basil Liddell-Hart (a renown military strategist) has reiterated "If you want peace, understand war" but to understand peace you first have to break it. Seldom is this achieved now, without drawing the wrath of civil law upon your head; but though what I am about to say will to many seem utterly ridiculous, it is ironical. True, this "breaking of peace" can be accomplished through history books. By observing human relations one can gain knowledge from past mistakes and put what you have

learnt into practical application - preferably for the better. Taking one of Mao Tse-tung's quotations on history from his "Selected Military Writings" we find that he claims "Reading is learning, but applying it is also learning and the more important kind of learning at that."

Looking to greater horizons the need to comprehend the factor of human endeavour and to avoid all unnecessary suffering and undue loss of life should be the main aim of everyone who studies history.

Yours etc.

M. DAVIDSON.

12 Plantation Drive,
Untali.

THE MANICA GAP.

The question often arises - Were there Portuguese traders in Manicaland in the 17th century and did they use the gap between the mountains near Untali, en route to Zimbabwe in the interior for the gold trade? The answer becomes apparent when one considers the evidence of Portuguese influence in the building of villages, in ways of life, pottery and evidence of Christianity. On Murahwa's Hill there is an old Rozwi village where one can plainly see the Portuguese way of building and setting out of the village. The walls or rather the main exterior walls were finished off with a Gothic touch.

Andre madre was the first man of Portuguese blood to have passed through the Manica gap up to what is now Penhalonga and up to a place called Hokwe which is thought to be Nyahokwe where Ziwa farm is today. From there he carried on up north to Gurumuchu which is now Tete and he then returned to the coast at Quelemane. But unfortunately he did not open up a trade route as we know it, but he showed the Shona how to know a white man when any came through and to trade with them. This of course

showed up when the Rozwi discovered the metal, gold in Manicaland. Referring to a map there is a gold belt filling the Manica Gap extending down to the south-east then breaking and reforming again in the Gutu area. This gives us more or less a straight line. By archaeological findings Portuguese forts or trading posts have been found. These lead up to the fact that Portuguese traders must have used this gap or if not by them by Africans instructed or employed by the Portuguese to bring gold to the coast where it was then sent to Portugal.

The Portuguese must have had a fort on the coast at which they could command all this. The only fort at the time was Nova Sofala. It was built by Pedro d'Anbaya and a few masons in the 16th century. It was built as a trading post for the interior so that Portugal could open up more land in Africa.

From evidence given by the indigenous people who were most inhospitable, the Portuguese heard of the great mountains which prevented anyone from seeing the other side. It was not until Andremedre passed through the Manica Gap that the Portuguese realised that there was a way of seeing further inland.

So gradually the Portuguese influence crept in through the Manica Gap and came into contact with the Rozwi people. These people were a great tribe who had originated from the Mt. Darwin area and gradually conquered the whole of the Eastern margin down to Zimbabwe and from evidence in further parts of the country it is possible to suggest that the Rozwi people did inhabit Murahwa's Hill between the late 17th century to the 19th century when it was abandoned.

The body found at Murahwa's Hill was that of a head man. They managed to identify the body by the structure of the skull or cranium. On this body they found a piece of an enameled candlestick which indicated that these people must have come into contact with the Portuguese because the candlesticks could only have been enamelled in the late 1700's.

Beads found at Sofala have been recognised at Zimbabwe. These beads have been split up into many groups, but there are only two groups which tie up with Zimbabwe and these are the Sodzi and Madi. Sodzi beads are large and cumbersome and only in black and white and Madi beads are small, neat and black, white or brick red. These have been found in both Sofala and in Zimbabwe and have been linked up by the gold belt and the trading posts.

By this one can see the great link up between the East coast and the interior. This would not have been had there not been a Gap through which explorers and traders had all passed to help build Rhodesia.

A. WAITON VD.

BOOK REVIEWS.

'THE BORDERER' - JUBILEE EDITION.

Sub-titled "A History of Umtali Girls' and Boys' High Schools 1896 - 1968" - this special edition was produced to coincide with and to commemorate the Jubilee Celebrations held in June, 1969 when sixty years of Government schooling in Umtali had been completed.

What constitutes history is an arguable question. If Edward Gibbon, of Decline and Fall fame, is to be believed, history is "little more than the register of the crimes, follies and misfortunes of mankind." Obviously the producers of this particular record were concerned to provide an account of the origins and development of Umtali High School and in such a form as to create general interest. No text-book this, but a readable account compiled on a chronological basis. This has meant that the average reader for whom the years of his or her own school attendance are of paramount interest can quickly recall events and personalities. For the reader of the history as a whole, there would, perhaps, have been an advantage if the chronological basis had been rejected for, say, a subject basis, but the casual purchaser will have far outnumbered the historians. In this light, a most surprisingly detailed but nonetheless readable account has emerged, which will surely have gone far to satisfy the intention. Well illustrated and attractively produced, it lacks only some positive identification of those responsible for its preparation. A Research Committee is certainly named and much work they obviously did, but who converted facts into readable material? One thing is manifest: the mass of information which was collected is now safely recorded, -- it cannot vanish with lost memories and discarded files. A worthwhile effort and a good result.

W.J.C.

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GERMAN EAST by Brian Gardner.

This book tells of the capture of German East Africa by the British, with the aid of South Africans, Indians and Belgians during the First World War. One of the first moves made was by the British and ill-equipped, badly trained Indian troops on the Port of Tanga. This action was comparable to the Crimean War in its blunders by the commander. The Indian troops, disheartened by a long sea voyage, were immediately sent into action. The commander, Brigadier General A.E. Aitken was so confident of thrashing the German African Askari that he refused any training in "bush-tactics" (like the British were so confident of taking Balaclava that they left vital troop equipment behind.) The net result was disaster. The Indians fled at the first German shots and mistaken for Germans themselves, were fired upon. The British then left on H.M.S. Fox leaving a greatly enriched German hold by the deserted ammunition and guns.

This event caused the British position to become defensive for some time to come, until Smuts and his South African troops reinforced them. Infiltrations into German territory were then made from Rhodesia, Belgian Congo, Uganda and headed by Smuts from British East Africa

(Kenya). The following campaign was lost till the end of the war while the German commander, Von Lettow-Vorbeck skillfully led a retreat which after running out of German territory in which to retreat continued at large causing much frustration and after penetrating half way into Portuguese East (Mozambique) and back, it finally halted at the end of the war 200 miles inside N. Rhodesia and still at large. Von Lettow-Vorbeck had employed some 130,000 British troops and cost the British some £72M. (not counting Portuguese and Belgian expenses). British casualties numbered 62,000 of whom 48,000 died from disease. The successful German hit and run tactics had caused much bother and made some interesting features.

But the main point in the whole campaign was that the two sides had to fight harder against the African diseases and bush than they did against their enemy. British supply was particularly poor as it was only late in the campaign when the whole coast area was taken (Tanga set back). In the rainy season all movement was brought to a stop while the land oozed mud.

The book is made interesting by the unusual conditions under which the war was fought. For example a telegraph line was constructed between two simultaneously advancing armies of the Belgians and the British but "unfortunately this line was continually being broken by giraffes." Also in the same Anglo-Belgian move the Author, Gardner, says this of a tribe of Africans employed to aid communications "the Rugga Rugga (the tribe) were also used by both sides as runners. They would trot for hours, even days, with a split stick held in front of them, a message fixed in the split. They hardly knew the difference between British and Germans and would show messages to any white man and seek further instructions. In this way both sides occasionally captured each other's orders."

The book combines humiliating defeat through disastrous misunderstanding with heroic determination and endurance, especially against disease and physical suffering. Often, writing about the World War I, historians tend to forget Africa, yet this book shows that the war in "German East" was one of the most interesting and outstanding campaigns of the whole war.

J.A. C.I.

A HISTORY OF EUROPE 1870 to 1950
by M.L.R. Isaac

A History of Europe written by M.L.R. Isaac, M.A. is a text-book of some merit but it does however possess several deficiencies. The book is primarily intended and I quote "to fulfil the requirements of the 'O' level syllabuses". If Isaac's intention was to provide a text-book for 'O' level students his choice of dates is indeed unfortunate, for in only covering the period 1870 to 1950 much of the syllabus has been neglected. To me the period 1789 to the Franco-Prussian war is indeed the most interesting and outstanding era in European history. This, to my mind, is a defect which severely lessens its usefulness as a text-book.

That section of history which the book does cover, however, is for the most part a comprehensive, un-opinionated study. Although the

book takes the form more of a novel than anything else, the relevant points are well set out accompanied by a sufficient amount of detail. I cannot help feeling, however, that the book would have been of more practical value had the author adopted an analytical style and laid down his information point by point.

Not given to waffle and irrelevancies, Isaac has in the main covered his topics with a deal of insight into them. The book is very readable as the style and methods of presentation are simple and as such I would unhesitatingly recommend it to anyone studying post 1870 European history.

B.K. C.I.

ALL QUIET ON THE WESTERN FRONT
by E.M. Remarque.

As this is a German story translated into English, the language is inclined to be very simple. It is a straightforward story dealing mainly with the trench-warfare of the First World War.

Basically it is the story of a young German soldier's life in the war. Initially he is a young and raw recruit reluctantly commissioned into the army together with his school friends. During the first year they rapidly acquire full manhood and, although they do not participate in the front line fighting, they emerge as hardened soldiers.

Thereafter engaged in the horrors of trench-warfare they are subjected for days on end to heavy bombing, artillery fire and the deadly threat of gas. They are confined to their trenches for long spells and food, water and sleep are hard come by. Casualties are high, particularly amongst the inexperienced recruits.

There is perhaps no better example revealing the author's emotions than when he is confined to a trench with a young French soldier whom he has mortally wounded. Previously the war had been a coldly impersonal affair and had meant little to him. Now, having stabbed the soldier, he realizes that his opponent is a fellow human being. He is full of belated repentance and suffers great mental anguish:

"Comrade, I did not want to kill you . . . But now, for the first time, I see you are a man like me."

Interspersed with the front line fighting are horrifying accounts of the German hospitals and the prisoner of war camps.

The reader is also informed of the writer's visits home to see his parents. These visits are emotional and serve to illustrate the writer's parents' pathetic and unrealistic understanding of the war. Their views, typical of the German civilians, are completely idealistic yet the young German soldier is unable to shatter their illusions.

The book has its lighter moments, as shown by the pranks undertaken by the writer and his comrades to secure food.

Gradually the author's friends are killed or maimed and are forced to leave the front. Ultimately he is the sole survivor of the original seven with whom he had joined the army. At the conclusion of the book a post script adds that the author was apparently killed on a day when all was "quiet on the Western Front". One can only feel that his death was a merciful release - . . . "his face had an expression of calm, as though almost glad the end had come."

This sad story is made even more distressing by the futility and wretchedness of the war. The author, very forthright in his ideas, captures the true war spirit in this accurate but disheartening account of the First World War.

R.H.C. C.I.

THE INFAMOUS MEAT HOOKS.

1 a.m. July 21st 1944; radio Germany . . .

"A very small clique of ambitious officers, devoid of conscience and at the same time criminally stupid, had forged a conspiracy to remove me . . ." Adolf Hitler.

This bland statement brought to light an 11 year struggle between Hitler and the Wehrmacht. Many of Germany's finest soldiers were either dismissed or executed on Hitler's orders; Von Brauchitch, Fritsch, Beck, Guderian, Haepner, Rommel, Kluge and Witzleben among them. The plot to depose Hitler would have been attempted in the late thirties had Hitler's foreign policy failed. It did not.

Many attempts on his life were made in the early years of the war, only to be foiled by Hitler's non-appearance or his erratic schedule.

A circle of liberals, Christians and worried generals was built around Col. Gen. Ludwig Beck. Beck was a man of high moral character and was a first rate soldier. In his view Hitler was leading Germany to ruin. Influential men like Fromm (Chief of the Army of the Interior) Canaris (head of counter espionage and Goerdeler (Mayor of Leipzig) were ready to, if not kill, at least depose Hitler.

Among the inner circles of the conspirators, it was felt Hitler would have to be killed at his Headquarters. These feelings crystallised into a plan to kill Hitler at his "Wolf's lair" near Rastenburg in East Prussia.

Upon Hitler's death troops in Berlin would seize the major Nazis and take over control of the machinery of Government. Similar coups were to be staged in each major centre. Peace would immediately be made with the Western powers and Germany saved. As it turned out only Stulpnagel in Paris managed to fulfil his task. He later attempted suicide but was hung despite it.

A one-armed, one eyed colonel, Claus von Stauffenberg, came forward to do the actual killing. A highly respected soldier, Stauffenberg was also a religious and cultured man. He supported Hitler at first but

soon changed when he saw the true meaning of the '1000 year Reich',

The events leading up to the attempt reads like a fantastic spy thriller. The method of death chosen was assassination by bomb. Strangely enough the bomb was of British make. Very simply it was a 10 minute fuse fitted into a slab of plastic explosive (Hexite). Britain had given these bombs to resistance movements and had been captured by the Abwehr (Counter Espionage),

Hitler had a mania for headquarters. He had one at Zozzen, Berchtesgaden (eagle's nest), many in Russia and one at Rastenberg. S.S. guards watched concentric lines of pill boxes, minefields and barbed wire. Keitel, Hitler's chief of Staff thought it like a concentration camp. Hitler himself lived and worked in Sperrkreis I the innermost enclosure. General Fellgiebel, an anti-Nazi was in charge of communications. He was to cut all radio and telephone links after Hitler's demise.

After his plane touched down in the early morning, Stauffenberg went through all the checkpoints to Sperrkreis I. He first met Keitel, who was worried as they were late. The bomb was wrapped in a shirt in Stauffenberg's brief case. When the clasp was opened it would break a glass phial of acid which would noiselessly set the fuse off. The conference was held in a wooden hut instead of the usual bunker. This fact was to have great implications later. The conference table was of solid oak and was supported by two heavy bulkheads. Stauffenberg stood a couple down on Hitler's right. He leant down and placed the case on Hitler's side of the nearest support. He opened the clasp at 12.37 p.m. on the 20th July, 1944 and excusing himself he left. The men round the table were staring as was usual at Hitler's conferences. Colonel Brant, on Stauffenberg's left, bumped the brief case and moved it to the other side of the bulkhead. Stauffenberg, smoking a cigarette outside, saw the hut blow up at 12.47p.m. dead on time. Fellgiebel did his job and Stauffenberg left. But Hitler was not dead. The bulkhead absorbed much of the blast and the lightness of the hut dissipated the effect.

The plan for Berlin was put into operation but was quickly crushed; 'he' was not dead. Hitler's anger at this was natural but the revenge was out of all proportion. 5,000 men and women, priests, professors and soldiers most of them ignorant of the plan, were hung, shot or forced into suicide. These people were among the best Germans then alive.

Not content with this, Hitler, after torture and ghastly mistrials by Freisler of the suspects had them hung up on meat hooks and issued films of them. Such disgusting sadism was past all bounds of reason. 5,000 people were sacrificed to this senseless perverted Moloch.*

References : "Shirt of Nessus" by Constantine Fitzgibbon.
"20th July 1944" issued by West German Information Bureau.
"Revolt of the Generals" see "Night of the Generals".

* Moloch was the God of Carthage. Babies were sacrificed to his bronze statue.